

NOAA'S NATIONAL UNDERSEA RESEARCH PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

NOAA's Office of Undersea Research supports numerous and diverse research on living resource assessment, marine pollution, geological processes, substrate or habitat response to external forces, and technology evaluation. This support of marine science is through several mechanisms. The principal being the submersible science programs and a network of Undersea Research Programs at various universities. The submersible science program consists of distinct, but complementary, elements. These include the partial support of the DSRV ALVIN and the leasing of shallow submersibles and remotely operated vehicles. Use of shallow submersible and remotely operated vehicles also is provided through most of the NURP university programs.

INTRODUCTION

NOAA's National Undersea Research Program (NURP) is the federal focus for support of marine research which requires the use of undersea vehicles or platforms. The range of this research is quite varied, being restricted only in the requirement to satisfy NOAA's goal of promoting fundamental and problem-oriented research and development of programs involving national needs and priorities. These research goals are consistent with Department of Commerce's goals of effective management of the nation's oceanic and atmospheric resources. To further NOAA's goal of a better understanding of the oceans and estuaries, NURP supports numerous and diverse research in living resource assessment, marine pollution, geological processes, substrate or habitat response to external forces, and technology development.

This program fills a unique niche in marine research. It, alone among the federal funding agencies, supports on a

routine basis research requiring the use of shallow manned submersibles, remotely operated vehicles, surface supported diving systems and sea floor sited habitats. These facilities permit scientists to observe, monitor, sample and manipulate aspects of the ocean environment first hand. Also, scientists can now sample on a scale heretofore not possible in the ocean environment. Sampling at very fine, discrete intervals within the water column, at the sediment-water interface, and the upper few centimeters of the ocean bottom, or in areas not accessible through sampling from a surface vessel provide researchers with important information otherwise not available.

HISTORY

In 1970, the Congress established the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) in the Department of Commerce. Among its many other charges and actions, this new agency assumed the responsibility within the federal government for developing a national program of undersea research supported by government, academia, and the private sector. Within NOAA, the Manned Undersea Science and Technology (MUS&T) Office was created to coordinate, oversee, and facilitate the development of man-in-the-sea marine science during the Agency's first decade. In 1980, following a series of internal and external reviews, the MUS&T program was reorganized to become the National Undersea Research Program (NURP). A major difference in the two programs is that the training of NOAA divers was spun off to become the NOAA Diving Program. The focus of the new undersea research program was to support quality academic, government and industry marine research through a variety of vehicles and facilities. These include manned submersibles, unmanned remotely operated vehicles, surface supported diving systems and habitats placed on the seafloor.

In 1985, the Administrator of NOAA commissioned a review of the need for undersea research throughout the federal government. Even though this study was much broader in scope than the NOAA Undersea Research Program, the findings of this committee had an obvious major impact on the program. Specific findings of the committee included:

NOAA should aggressively accept its historic ocean charter and provide national leadership in ocean research. Furthermore, NOAA should continue assuming the responsibility for developing and implementing a focused, national undersea science program to address research questions in the third dimension, that is from the sea surface down to and including the sea floor. Five high-priority research areas identified by the committee were:

Biological Productivity and Living Resources

Ocean Lithosphere and Mineral Resources

Pathways and Fate of Materials in the Ocean

Coastal Ocean and Estuarine Processes

Global Oceanic and Climatic Processes

Support of undersea research should be on a national level. This implies that: 1) NURP will represent each section of the country equally; and 2) Quality science proposals from academia, industry, NOAA, and other Federal agency scientists will be considered for funding support.

With the exception of habitats and deep diving submersibles (greater than 4,000m) the focus of NOAA's Undersea Research Program should be on leased facilities.

Support for science, in addition to providing for vehicles and facilities, is necessary.

Close collaboration and cooperation with other federal funding agencies is required.

ORGANIZATION

The Office of Undersea Research support of marine science is administered through: a submersible science program, diving research and development program

and national undersea research programs sited at five universities.

Submersible Science Program

The submersible science program is divided into two parts: the deep and the shallow submersible programs. For the deep submersible program, NOAA supports 20% of the Deep Submergence Research Vessel (DSRV) ALVIN operating expenses.

The shallow submersible program solicits research proposals on a national basis for projects which require the use of shallow manned submersibles or unmanned remotely operated vehicles. Shallow submersibles, for the purpose of this program, means manned vehicles with a maximum dive depth of 2500m or less.

Solicitation and review of these proposals are conducted through the Office of Undersea Research in Rockville, Maryland. The review process is on a competitive basis, using both mail reviews and a panel evaluation. Once a decision has been to support a research project, the Office of Undersea Research works directly with the principal investigator to determine the facilities and instrumentation requirements. Once these are established, the Office leases the appropriate vehicle.

Diving Research and Development Program

Research on diving physiology and hyperbaric medicine also is supported through the Office of Undersea Research. The Outer Continental Shelf Lands Act, Amended 1978, Section 21(e) provides the legislative mandate for this NOAA responsibility, which has as its objective the improvement of our capability to place man safely underwater to conduct research. The Office works cooperatively with the U.S. Navy, Undersea Medical Society, and others conducting research as well as holding workshops and symposiums.

Some areas of particular research interest include the epidemiology of microbiological hazards associated with diving in polluted waters, diving safety, development and validation of diving tables for habitat operations, and development of criteria to evaluate an individual's fitness to dive.

University-based National Undersea Research Programs

The five university-based programs are: Fairleigh Dickinson University (West Indies Laboratory, St. Croix), University

of Connecticut (Avery Point Campus), University of North Carolina-Wilmington, University of Southern California, and the University of Hawaii. These programs differ as to their capability and thus as to the type of undersea research supported. The first and perhaps best known of these programs is the habitat in St. Croix (Fairleigh Dickinson University). The original Hydrolab was recently replaced by a larger, mobile, and thus more versatile habitat. Historically research at the St. Croix facility has focused on biological productivity (including nutrient cycling and larval fish recruitment), pathways and fate of pollutants, coastal processes, and ocean lithosphere studies in the area of Salt River Canyon off the coast of St. Croix. With the mobility of a new habitat, the plan is to develop long-term multidisciplinary research programs in support of a Caribbean Basin Initiative. The research themes for this program will focus on the enhancement of the region's marine resources, training of local scientists in undersea research, techniques, and technology transfer.

The program at the University of North Carolina- Wilmington utilizes a small research vessel with a diving bell and mixed gases to support a multitude of projects on the continental shelf of eastern United States. The research focus is on coastal processes, artificial reefs, and biological productivity.

NOAA's Undersea Research Program at the University of Connecticut is one of the first programs to adopt a total lease approach for providing undersea vehicles to the science community. The concept of leasing, plus a multidisciplinary science approach, appears to meet effectively most of the highly varied needs of the research community in the Great Lakes, the Gulf of Maine, and southern New England. The focus of this research is resource assessment, benthic productivity, coastal processes, fate and effects of pollutants, and ocean lithosphere studies.

The program at the University of Hawaii addresses the research requirements of the central and western Pacific. Support is provided through the use of two submersibles with diving capabilities of 350 m and 2000 m and a small remotely operated vehicle. The science focus of the program is in the areas of biological productivity (particularly seamount ecology), ocean lithosphere studies in the hydrothermal vent systems, fate and pathways of pollutants, and global oceanic processes.

The program at the University of Southern California is being redirected from a habitat and tether diving program to one which leases manned and unmanned vehicles. The research focus is expected to be in the areas of biological productivity (both benthic and in the water column), coastal processes, physical oceanographic processes, and ocean lithosphere studies.

These university based undersea research programs participate in the national solicitation conducted by the Office of Undersea Research. Through this solicitation, potential researchers are made aware of the unique capabilities and means of accessing the complementary university programs. Following the national solicitation, the university programs conduct their own solicitation. This second solicitation is directed toward researchers who may require the facilities available at a given university based program but who may have missed the national solicitation. Following the solicitation, the undersea research university programs conduct a two step peer review consisting of mail reviews followed by an on-site evaluation.

FUTURE RESEARCH STRATEGY AND PLAN

The five high priority research areas identified by the committee reporting on national undersea research requirements to the Administrator of NOAA will provide the initial science focus for the new Undersea Research Program. Imbedded within the various areas are general categories for research. These categories are not mutually exclusive; in fact strong linkages often exist between research areas. Similar linkages may exist between the broader research areas. Thus, the support of undersea research in one of these areas often actually addresses research needs in several of the other areas.

Biological Productivity and Living Resources

Research in this area is critically needed to improve the understanding of the biological productivity in the sea, the causes of the variations, and the ability of the oceans to provide the living resources required by man. Benefits of such research include new insight into food chain dynamics, thus allowing a better understanding of the higher consumers (secondary productivity), and improved knowledge of biological and environmental factors controlling recruitment in animal stocks. Such knowledge enhances our understanding

and prediction of intrannual variation in these stocks.

Ocean Lithosphere and Mineral Resources

Previous marine geoscience research has done much to improve our understanding of the mechanisms and processes responsible for the geological and tectonic setting on a global scale. Based on these findings and with the improved technology, it is now possible to conduct effective studies to investigate the mechanisms and processes associated with the evolution of the ocean basin and materials comprising the seafloor. Without this understanding, we lack sufficient knowledge to explain the tectonic stress, earthquake activity, or the formation of mineral deposits on land as well as the sea floor.

Mineral resources represent an obvious example of potentially significant resources associated with the sea floor. Included among these sea floor minerals are many which the U.S. largely imports from politically unfriendly or unstable countries. Recent actions, like the passage of the Deep Seabed Hard Mineral Resources Act, the Presidential proclamation of a 200-mile Exclusive Economic Zone, and passage of the Arctic Research and Policy Act, reflect the national concern over access to important strategic minerals.

Pathways and Fates of Materials

During the last few decades, man induced stresses on ocean and coastal ecosystems have increased exponentially. Predicting the impact of these stresses requires a detailed understanding of the interactive physical, chemical, geological and biological processes associated with these ecosystems. Recent studies have markedly altered our view of both the estuaries and oceans. For example, due to our better understanding of the ocean's role in producing acidic precursors and the chemical nature of hydrothermal vent fluids we no longer view the ocean as only a passive "sink".

Understanding how toxic and non-toxic materials are transformed and transported vertically within the water column and horizontally from the coasts across the continental shelf and in the deep ocean is the primary goal for this area of research. Such research is particularly important as the recent focus on the ocean as an alternative to land disposal for a variety of wastes increases. Providing sufficient environmental safeguards without unnecessarily restrictive or costly regulations requires a clear understanding of how the

ocean will respond to the introduction of materials.

Global Oceanic and Climatic Processes

The application of new technology has resulted in a shift in our thinking of the oceans and climate from that of a regional to a global perspective. Nowhere is this more apparent than in the area of coupling of oceanic and atmospheric processes. We now know that the tropical oceans interact with the global atmosphere to cause climate anomalies associated with the El Nino phenomenon. Ejection of material from volcanos can lead to global cooling, whereas the increased concentration of gases such as carbon dioxide, methane, and chlorofluoromethanes in the atmosphere can lead to global temperature change. Long-term decreases in upper atmospheric ozone caused by increases in oxides of nitrogen and chlorine can cause increased penetration of ultraviolet radiation. The cycles of carbon, sulfur, phosphorus, nitrogen, and water are all affected by storage and transfer between the atmosphere, the ocean, the biota, and the solid earth. By recognizing the nature and magnitude of this coupling, it will be possible to predict climatic changes on annual scales. Conceivably, this prediction can be extended over even longer time scales.

Coastal Ocean and Estuarine Processes

Within the next decade 75 percent of the United States population will live within 50 miles of the ocean, Great Lakes or the watersheds of estuaries. As such, our coastal environment will be placed under increasing stress. Understanding the impact of this stress is made more difficult by the complexity and variability of these ecosystems. Characteristic properties which change on time scales of hours in these areas change by comparable amounts in the open ocean only over periods of years, decades, or even centuries. Comparable spatial variability is found. Changes of properties which occur over distances of a few meters in the vertical and a few kilometers in the horizontal in the coastal ocean and estuaries, occur in the open ocean only over distances of tens to hundreds of meters in the vertical and thousands to tens of thousands of kilometers in the horizontal. Man's impact on the natural processes of these systems have wrought changes which in the open ocean would occur only over geologic time spans. Understanding the natural processes and their biological consequences and separating these from the effects of society are required

before effective management strategies can be formulated.

SUMMARY

Undersea research facilities, available to the researchers through NOAA's Undersea Research Program, permit scientists to observe, monitor, sample and manipulate aspects of the ocean environment first hand. Sampling at very fine, discrete intervals within the water column, at the sediment-water interface, and the upper few centimeters of the ocean bottom, or in areas not accessible through sampling from a surface vessel provides researchers with important in situ information not otherwise available.